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EIRENE RI Strategic Plan

for 2025-2030: implementation period

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Executive Summary

EIRENE RI (Research Infrastructure for Environmental Exposure assessment in Europe) is the first European research infrastructure focused on human exposome research - studying environmental exposures and their health impacts. EIRENE RI entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2021 and is now close to the end of the Preparatory Phase. EIRENE RI addresses the growing evidence linking environmental factors to non-communicable diseases through a holistic approach that considers indoor and outdoor environments, socioeconomic factors, lifestyle, and individual stress responses.

The EIRENE consortium includes **21 European countries, the USA, Australia, Canada and Japan**. Since it is currently the only large research infrastructure worldwide focusing on Exposome research, it aims to attract all the major actors in the field from across the globe.

The infrastructure combines advanced analytical technologies and harmonized data collection, integration and interpretation methods to study exposure-health relationships. By uniting leading EU and US researchers, EIRENE RI aims to provide standardized workflows and open-access tools for academia, industry, public authorities, and citizens.

The coordinated approach aims to strengthen global research capabilities, support evidence-based policymaking, and ultimately improve understanding of environmental impacts on human health for better protection of EU citizens.

EIRENE aims **to fill this gap in our understanding of human health and disease** by integrating exposomics into biomedical research, innovation, and practice. The **EIRENE's vision** is to develop not only European but global infrastructural capacities enabling agnostic studies allowing the discovery of unforeseen links between stressors and impacts.

The main strategic goal for the period of 2026-2030 is to become operational distributed research infrastructure providing its services to variety of users and delivering high value to science and society.

1 EIRENE RI in brief

EIRENE RI (Research Infrastructure for Environmental Exposure assessment in Europe) entered the ESFIR roadmap in 2021 to be the first European research infrastructure focused on human exposome research. This initiated its preparatory phase supported by the EU-funded EIRENE PPP project. The preparatory work has laid foundation for a consolidated pan-European research infrastructure dedicated to the development of advanced technologies and complementary services for characterizing complex environmental exposures and their impacts on the European population.

Understanding the human exposome

People differ in their genetic predispositions, which determine 20-70% (depending on the type of disease) of whether we stay healthy or develop chronic diseases. Health is the result of an interaction between the human genome and non-genetic factors collectively referred to as the exposome. These include natural, work and home environments, exposure to toxic substances, nutrition and dietary habits, lifestyle, physical activity, alcohol, drug or alcohol use, smoking, but also socio-economic circumstances and psychological stress. A better understanding of the cumulative effects of these influences is essential for the further development of precision (tailored or personalized) medicine and preventive measures.

EIRENE RI addresses the growing evidence linking environmental factors to non-communicable diseases through a holistic approach that considers indoor and outdoor environments, socioeconomic factors, lifestyle, and individual stress responses. The infrastructure combines advanced analytical technologies and harmonized data collection, integration and interpretation methods to study exposure-health relationships. By uniting leading EU and US researchers, EIRENE RI aims to provide standardized workflows and open-access tools for academia, industry, public authorities, and citizens.

EIRENE members

The EIRENE consortium includes 21 European countries, the USA, Australia, the negotiations are held with Japan and Canada. In the future, EIRENE intends to expand its reach CEE countries and to other continents. Since it is currently the only large research infrastructure worldwide focusing on Exposome research, it hopes to attract all the major actors in the field from across the globe.

2 Vision and Mission

Vision

Our vision is for EIRENE to play a **pivotal role in uncovering non-genetic factors** that contribute to chronic conditions, ultimately **enhancing the health and well-being of the population**.

With a long tradition of environmental monitoring and cohort studies, registers, and biobanks, Europe has a comparative advantage. To capitalize on it, the researchers should be supported by a sustainable network of research infrastructures to enhance the exploitation of existing, while allowing, for the synergistic and harmonised development of new capacities. This will support excellent research towards an improved understanding of environmental exposures and their potential health impacts, generation of validated data for evidence-based policy making for adequate protection of human health and the further development of the concept of personalized medicine and prevention. EIRENE RI should complement existing ESFRI infrastructures to provide additional expertise while avoiding unnecessary duplicity.

Mission

Our **mission** is to establish a sustainable open access research infrastructure **enabling the advancement of exposome research in Europe** by bringing together **complementary capacities** available in the member states, **harmonizing them and upgrading** to address current scientific and societal challenges in the areas of chemical exposures and population health.

In the short term, EIRENE will integrate complementary capacities of the infrastructures available in ERA, enhance cooperation between the initiatives at the EU and national levels and exploitation of existing monitoring and biomonitoring programmes, population cohorts and samples, experimental facilities and information databases. EIRENE will build on European excellence and strengthen the focus on education, training, capacity building, knowledge transfer, and the spreading of best practice.

In the long-term, it will allow for the development of improved and harmonized methods for sampling, sample analysis, and data management, validated exposure and effect biomarkers. The innovative approaches will help to decipher the potential causal associations between exposures to toxic mixtures over a lifetime and health effects and to understand the mechanisms of these associations.

It will close the gap between the fields of environmental and health sciences, eliminate fragmentation of environmental and health data in Europe and enable more efficient application and exploitation of available knowledge for improved risk assessment, chemical management, evidence-based regulation and sound policy-making in a wide variety of sectors for better protection of the health of EU citizens. EIRENE will also contribute to the development of innovative health policies and better healthcare provision and at the same time, enhance the industrial competitiveness by developing new exposure, effect, and susceptibility biomarkers, improved analytical and risk assessment methods.

3 Key challenges

The most important challenge for the implementation phase is to secure strong political and financial support and firm commitment from EIRENE member states. While EIRENE has raised interest in many countries, including those beyond the European border, and has gotten a lot of political support since the adoption to the ESFRI Roadmap, the future of the RI agenda is not very clear at both the national and European levels.

The human exposome represents a global scientific challenge. Moreover, the growing concerns around environmental and health justice require urgent attention and coordinated action. EIRENE will contribute by its research capabilities and datasets—both current and planned— and will provide essential evidence for policymakers across local, national, and international levels. However, securing active participation and support from low- and middle-income countries presents another significant challenge, potentially limiting the infrastructure's global reach and impact. In this sense, there is a risk that these activities will remain a privilege of the “global north”.

A need to assess both internal and external exposome poses several technical and methodological problems. While the target analyses of biological samples are time-intensive and costly, non-target approaches touch the technical limits of current instrumentation and lack sufficient IT solutions. There is also a need for innovations in micro-sampling, sensing, and wearable technologies. This can be an advantage at the same time since it makes collaboration more attractive also for the private sector.

Legal and ethical issues must also be considered because exposome research is like genomics and other omics, dealing with sensitive personal data. A willingness to look for legal solutions is needed, together with the availability of safe IT technologies that protect sensitive data. A need to share data and samples globally raises even more concern. Even the need to establish some global legal bonds between institutions does not have trivial practical solutions.

EIRENE directly contributes to Horizon Europe's missions of cancer and smart cities through the development of new tools and methods. Two of six HEU clusters specifically define intervention areas highly relevant to EIRENE, e.g., Health throughout the life course, Environmental and social health determinants or Tools, technologies, and digital solutions for health and care, including personalized medicine in the Health Cluster. Globally, EIRENE RI is relevant for tackling SDG3 on Health, SDG11 on Sustainable cities, SDG6 on Clean water and sanitation, and SDG9 on Infrastructures.

The Draghi report emphasizes utilizing secondary use of health and patient data to support health research, including building large AI models to support the European research and pharma industry. EU Chemical Strategy for Sustainability strategy commits to supporting research on the human exposome to better understand the cumulative impacts of chemical exposures across different life stages and calls for improved methodologies and tools to incorporate exposome data into chemical safety assessments and regulatory decision-making. Building on cooperation with EU RIs, partnerships, and joint projects, EIRENE leverages investments into European initiatives such as European Health Data Space or EOSC and aims to provide relevant, reliable, and readily accessible scientific data vital for the implementation of both strategies.

4 Our context

The European Union is facing increasingly complex and interconnected health and environmental challenges. The growing burden of both infectious and non-communicable diseases—such as neurodegenerative, cardiometabolic, immune-mediated diseases, and cancer—is closely linked to environmental exposures and anthropogenic stressors. A growing body of evidence underscores the critical role of environmental determinants—air and water quality, chemical exposures, built environments, occupational hazards, and food systems—in shaping health trajectories across the lifespan. These stressors are amplified by climate change, biodiversity loss, and globalized industrial and agricultural practices. The environmental impacts are not evenly distributed and often disproportionately affect vulnerable and underserved populations, further reinforcing health inequities and undermining social cohesion—issues at the heart of the EU’s Health Union and European Pillar of Social Rights.

To respond effectively, a **multi-sectoral One Health approach**—integrating human, animal, and ecosystem health—is essential. The One Health framework is increasingly recognised across EU policies (e.g. the EU Green Deal, Biodiversity Strategy, and Farm to Fork Strategy) as a critical approach to addressing planetary health risks. However, the practical implementation of this approach is currently limited by disciplinary silos.

The **exposome concept** offers a unifying scientific framework to address this gap. By holistic consideration of the environmental exposures (i.e. non-genetic factors) that influence phenotype and health over the life course, the exposome science **enables a systems-level understanding of how the environment influences health**. Exposomics represents a transformative paradigm for health research as it goes beyond traditional risk assessment by incorporating multi-domain high-resolution longitudinal data, making the exposome concept particularly well-suited framework for precision public health and prevention strategies. This integrative approach promotes the interdisciplinary evaluation of a wide array of factors originating from natural, built-in, and social environments, occupation, lifestyle, and diet, which can be measured both outside (external component of the exposome), and in the human body (internal component of the exposome), and encourages environmental, clinical and social scientists to deliver a systematic and comprehensive mapping of these factors together with biological responses of the organism, to understand their contributions to disease risks.

Several application areas of this holistic approach have been identified in the STOA report presented to the European Parliament in 2025. In the **chemical domain**, exposomics evaluates real-world exposures, including cumulative and low-dose effects of industrial pollutants, supporting regulations like REACH, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, and the Clean Industrial Deal. **In child health**, it helps to identify early-life environmental risks (e.g. air pollution or endocrine disruptors) shaping long-term health, aligning with the European Child Guarantee and WHO’s strategy on child and adolescent health. For **occupational health**, exposomics helps monitor hazardous workplace exposures and anticipate risks from new industrial processes, informing the EU Strategic Framework on Health and Safety at Work. The holistic concept of exposome adapts the “triple crisis” considering joint pressures of **chemical pollution, climate change and biodiversity loss**. It addresses health risks linked to heat stress, air pollution, and wildfires, changes in plant, animal and ecosystem, impacting food production, directly informing adaptation policies such as the 2040 European Climate Law and the One Health Strategy. It improves **city planning** by identifying air and noise pollution sources and assessing environmental quality, both indoors and outdoors, helping to shape healthier, more sustainable cities in line with strategies such as the European Strategy for Housing and Construction, Sustainable Transport Investment Plan, the Climate Adaptation Plan, and the New European Bauhaus. Exposomics, however, also empowers **citizens** by providing exposure data that support informed health decisions, public awareness, and participatory governance, reflecting priorities under the European Green Deal and Real Deal Project. Implementation of exposomics to **clinical practice** enhances precision medicine by uncovering environmental drivers of disease, contributing to early diagnosis, prevention, and

personalised treatment approaches aligned with initiatives such as the Mental Health Plan and EU Mission on Cancer. This also opens a door to biomedical innovations and increased European competitiveness.

5 EIRENE Strategy for the implementation phase

During the implementation phase, EIRENE will complete the final steps towards becoming operational. This phase involves several key tasks, namely establishment of the legal and governance structure, development of financial framework, the technical implementation and development of services, networks and relationships with internal and external stakeholders and customers.

The implementation phase requires substantial coordination between participating countries and institutions to achieve a consent on future organizational and financial arrangements being the cornerstone of successful ERIC application, its establishment and long-term operation. Success in this specific phase is critical to reach operational status and serving its user community effectively on full-scale.

The ESFRI Public Roadmap 2026 Guide¹ clearly specifies the minimal key requirements for both the scientific and implementation (organizational) case. These requirements, defining the roadmap to operation and clarifying aspects and areas which will be evaluated and monitored by ESFRI, are therefore defining the **goals to be achieved within the Implementation phase**. These, subsequently, define the strategic goals of EIRENE RI for the implementation period.

The main strategic goal for the period of 2025-2030 is to **become operational distributed research infrastructure providing its services to variety of users and delivering high value to science and society**.

The specific goals of EIRENE RI in the implementation period are to:

Drive the scientific excellence and innovation in environmental health research, and enable to pioneer the research in human exposome via providing specialized and expert services to user community.

Consolidate the consortium and substantiate stakeholder's commitments and confirm viable economic, operational and technical model of EIRENE.

Establish the legal structure (EIRENE ERIC), implement effective governance and managerial model and employ key staff.

Implement data infrastructures and models for effective data management.

Develop, engage and train broad EIRENE user and provider community.

Deliver the value for European citizens, enhancing the recognition and international dimension of EIRENE.

¹ https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_Roadmap2026_Public%20Guide_approved_FINAL.pdf

6 Action plan

The specific aims are followed by the action plan defining the activities to be performed in defined areas – according to specific objectives – to achieve the main strategic goal specified above. Based on our experiences from the preparatory phase and the experiences of mature research infrastructures, which have already passed the implementation phase, major efforts will be paid to reassuring and achieving the support of member states and all relevant parties on the form, scale and scope of future legal entity and its operational and financial arrangements. These are crucial aspects of EIRENE RI's development enabling its operation and service provision.

Developing services for scientific excellence and innovation in environmental health

EIRENE RI is committed to drive excellent research in the area of human exposome and environmental health sciences. As such, EIRENE RI aims to provide excellent services and expertise, which are based on latest scientific knowledge and innovation, recent research methodologies and tools, trusted data and quality assured repositories. Moreover, the ambition of EIRENE is not only to utilize recent scientific knowledge, but to actively contribute to the advancements of human exposome research field and development of high-end methodologies, tools and pipelines, including their standardization and quality management.

To achieve that, EIRENE RI will:

- Continuously analyze the evolving scientific landscape, policy needs and expectations of users to update the EIRENE scientific strategy and availability of services,
- Finalize the distributed architecture of the infrastructure and agree on the roles of national nodes, centralized services and reference laboratories,
- Consolidate the portfolio of research services, expertise and data resources, both already existing and still developing,
- Develop and implement the standardization and harmonization plans as part of the quality assurance and control of EIRENE,
- Implement the access policies to distributed services and develop unified system / entry point for user-friendly access procedures and management.

Consolidating EIRENE and achieving the stakeholder's commitments on viable economic, operational and technical model of EIRENE

EIRENE RI will create the backbone research infrastructure for the research of exposome based on international cooperation using the synergies of existing and developing infrastructures and expertise all over the Europe. The commitment of participating institutions and namely the national authorities is crucial for further development and to set the adequate scope and scale of services of both the national and central facilities and of the head office.

To achieve that, EIRENE RI will:

- Consolidate the EIRENE RI consortium and seek for membership enlargement to create strong core-group,
- Further develop the interim General Assembly (GA) assuring the representation of the whole consortium, and to update its Terms of Reference,
- Update operational, technical, economical and financial model of EIRENE RI as part as Updated EIRENE Business model, which will be approved by the interim GA,

- Confirm the legal form of EIRENE RI for operation phase and the support of national nodes and stakeholders,
- Achieve the commitment of national representatives (interim GA) on structure, organizational and financial aspects of future EIRENE ERIC, and factually
- Secure the funding for a long term operation of EIRENE RI and establish contribution mechanisms.

Establishing the legal structure and implement effective governance

To serve as the global research infrastructure, EIRENE needs to develop professional management, effective governance and appropriate legal structure, which is ready to provide appropriate level of services to both the users and EIRENE members. Following the example of mature research infrastructures, the ERIC legal form is appropriate solution and effective legal model. As such, the aim is to submit the application for ERIC within the implementation phase and to become operational already as the ERIC no later than 2030.

To achieve that, EIRENE RI will:

- Develop and implement effective governance and management structure, which will follow the needs of the consortium, reflect the expectations of stakeholders and consider the experiences of mature research infrastructures,
- Agree on the legal framework of EIRENE RI for operation and develop the legal framework and complex set of documents to be able to submit the ERIC application within the implementation phase,
- Develop internal rules, policies and documents to serve as the framework for operation, including the documents and strategies of staffing, human resources in general, procurement, ethics etc.,
- Set the legal entity for Operation phase.

Implementing data infrastructures and models for effective data management

EIRENE responds to the need to facilitate research into human health and well-being at all life stages, accounting for environmental, sociological, and economic drivers. This complex interdisciplinary research environment, involving widely varying institutions, will require an extremely well-curated approach to data acquisition, documentation, storage, and dissemination. As such, EIRENE needs to have well defined relation to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) creating the environment for easy data access, publishing and re-using.

To achieve that, EIRENE RI will:

- Define the data services, data management strategies and workflows,
- Specify the Data infrastructure of EIRENE, including possible creation of EIRENE Data Centre / Hub, development of sustainable data and ICT policy or EIRENE,
- Develop and implement robust Data policy and data management solution suitable for EIRENE Users and Providers, with respect to FAIR and European and global open access policies,
- Update and implement the EIRENE Data Management Plan based on services to be provided and participating partners, their capacities and provided services,
- Specify the relationship to the European Open Science Cloud and relations to its services from both the user and provider perspective.

Engaging and providing training to EIRENE user and service provider community

EIRENE aims to provide the access to a broad variety of high-quality and complex services, resources and expertise to a wide range of users from academia, industry or policy-making environment. The users are therefore one of our key stakeholders, and are placed into the centre of EIRENE's interest. Therefore, we will focus not only on the user attraction and training, but also on the engagement of users as regular customers participating on co-designing of services or service quality evaluation.

To achieve that, EIRENE RI will:

- Develop and implement robust User strategy,
- Continuously communicate and interact with users with the ambition to expand to new users,
- Identify and understand their needs to properly define and promote our services and their added value,
- Map user experience and feedback to adjust and improve existing processes, policies and services to ensure their satisfaction and to answer their needs,
- To implement the training strategy for both the users and providers,
- To offer training and education as one of the EIRENE services.

Demonstrating the value at European and global scale and consolidating international dimension

The environmental pollution and exposure to harmful chemicals together with dramatic changes in ecosystem services represent a combination of issues that require an integrated approach at a pan-European and global level. EIRENE RI offers to develop European capacities for assessment of the chemical exposure component of the human exposome concept by taking a comprehensive approach to the assessment of effects of environmental exposures on human health and disease throughout the human lifetime. Beside advancing the field and provision of actual services, EIRENE will demonstrate its value and the value of the exposome research to the society, science and innovation at the global scale and will seek for synergies, complementarities and possibilities of cooperation with relevant partners.

To achieve that, EIRENE RI will:

- Continuously develop the relationships with stakeholder communities at national, European and global level,
- Establish and further develop the partnership with the other research infrastructures,
- Partner with non-European research infrastructures, institutions and regions,
- Create links with industry and other relevant sectors,
- Develop international collaborations and consolidate its international dimension,
- Develop and implement dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies,
- Develop and communicate show- and use cases demonstrating the added value of EIRENE (scientific, technical, innovation and social).

Next steps

The EIRENE Strategic Plan for the implementation phase represents five-year roadmap to its operation. This strategy, together with the comprehensive action plan define the key steps and milestones, which are necessary for the smooth transition from the design of idea and preparation of EIRENE RI framework to daily life of excellence-driven and user-centered research infrastructure. It sets the goals and objectives for all EIRENE partners and stakeholders at all levels – institutional, national, international, intergovernmental and global.

Numerous steps and activities will be supported by national and European project, implementation of which would allow to reach the above formulated goal. This strategy is therefore blueprint and cornerstone for these projects and will be used accordingly.

The strategy will be regularly updated and its fulfilment will be annually assessed and the progress communicated within the consortium and the relevant stakeholders.

The implementation of this strategy will enable us to realise our vision, which is to **“contribute to unravelling non-genetic factors behind the development of chronic conditions and to improvement of the population health.”**

7 Value of EIRENE

Scientific Impact

EIRENE will mediate an open access to the distributed research infrastructures supporting a world-class research expanding the scientific knowledge in the area of human exposome, supporting the development of new technologies and translation of the research results to the daily lives of citizens via public-private (industry, spin-offs) or public-public (policy-making) partnerships in order to tackle a problem of nongenetic factors behind the development of chronic conditions and to improve the population health. In the short term, launching these methods in the high-throughput facilities will enable a new generation of large-scale studies focused on better understanding of the impact of various factors on the onset and development of diseases.

Such infrastructural capacity will then be applied to screen the datasets of well-designed and harmonized cohort studies to ensure adequate statistical power needed for health impact assessment of combined exposures. Better coordination of existing and future cohort studies including e.g. parent-child, adult, occupation, ageing, genomic and patients information is needed to capture exposures throughout the life course. In the long term, harmonized sample and data collection methods would produce comparable data, enabling also meta-analyses across different datasets and comparisons with different statistical approaches to improve our knowledge and understanding of disease aetiology and to help identifying factors affecting health.

The integration of the outcomes of the human health-relevant toxicological models and the state-of-the-art exposure models will further contribute to identification of the major drivers of toxicity. In vitro, ex vivo and in silico studies will help to identify causal exposure-response relationships and to better understand the underlying biological and biochemical processes. Translational human in vitro cell model systems (organs-on-a-chip) as well as cellular models will be used and combined with adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) modelling to explore connection between molecular initiation events, key events, and adverse outcomes. This will contribute to identification of early markers of disbalance and effect potentially applicable for the diagnosis of preclinical stages of selected diseases.

Improved data sharing and integration between various human and environmental surveys is another important impact on future infrastructural landscape enabling joint interpretation of data across sectors, disciplines and multiple stakeholders, and development of new prediction models, prevention, and intervention strategies. The outcomes of such efforts will be available to both the scientific community and policy makers to inform evidence-based decision taking for the adequate protection of human health and better healthcare. It should be noted that interpretation of high-resolution exposure and metabolic profiles will require advanced statistical and bioinformatics approaches.

The objectives of such studies cannot be reached without development of computational tools that maximize information gain from the experimental work. The statistical pipelines will be established together with sufficient data storage, management, analysis, and interpretation capacities enabling FAIR data management and integrative analysis across multidimensional omics (i.e. exposomics, metabolomics, genomics, epigenomics, metagenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics) data.

Societal Impact

The most important strategic framework relevant for EIRENE is the EU Green Deal which sets new strategies containing ambitious targets for a wide range of topics, including environmental and health protection from chemicals (Zero Pollution Ambition). It aims to address the exposure of European populations to a wide range of chemicals and their mixtures through diet, consumer products, water, ambient air, indoor environments, and occupations. The path towards eliminating the most dangerous chemicals, tightening the rules for their production and use, strengthening the

competitiveness of the European chemical industry, and ensuring long-term sustainability in this area has been set out by the EU Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, published in October 2020. However, to address these long-standing challenges at the European level, EU policy must be based on translating the latest scientific knowledge into measures for protecting the environment and the health of European citizens in accordance with Article 191 TFEU. As relevant, reliable, and readily accessible scientific data is required for sound and adaptive management of environmental quality and public health and such data are currently not always available, the EIRENE Research infrastructure will be instrumental for the successful implementation of the SU Chemical strategy and achievement of ambitious goals of the Zero Pollution.

EIRENE RI activities are highly relevant for successful fulfilment of all Horizon Europe Missions. Identification of environmental drivers of chronic diseases, for instance, is relevant for Mission “Cancer” in the area of “Prevention and early detection”. Several EIRENE partners are already collaborating (and also collaborating with IARC) within the cancer-oriented research projects such as EOSC4Cancer or DISCERN. Joint addressing the “triple” (climate, pollution, biodiversity) crises is crucial for successful solutions in Mission “A Climate Resilient Europe.” New methodologies for chemical risk assessment and management, however, are beneficial also for Missions focused on Water, Soil and Food, or Urban Environments.

Ensuring more efficient access and exploitation of datasets and pursuing interoperability of data, metadata, products, and services in a full, open, and unrestricted manner would generate business opportunities for the private sector leading to significant benefits to European society as a whole. Joint research activities focused on developing protocols for the complex characterization of human internal chemical exposure and biological responses through integrated targeted, suspect, and non-targeted screening approaches will likely result in novel analytical and bioinformatics technologies that can be translated into innovative products. New analytical approaches will enable identification, characterization, and validation of predictive markers of effects and chronic health impacts with the application potential in the diagnosis of early, preclinical stages of multifactorial diseases which can be developed into novel biomedical products. This might be of interest for biotechnology and pharmaceutical companies searching for new diagnostic tools and specific markers for characterization and stratification of patients. Such research will result in advances in personalised medicine offering again new opportunities to the private sector. Virtual labs will translate research results into applicable knowledge offering new insights to decision makers at all levels but also new opportunities for industries and SMEs.

Added Value of EIRENE ERIC

The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) legal framework delivers governance and coordination mechanisms for unified distributed operations, managed by the central administration hub - EIRENE-ERIC Head Office. This structure amplifies individual Node and Operator capabilities by establishing shared strategic guidelines, global recognition, standardized service protocols and data integration, plus strong ties to EU Research Programs. The ERIC acts as a unifying force for the operator network, aligning collective goals and operational structures while achieving cost efficiencies and balanced Infrastructure growth responsive to stakeholder requirements. This establishes the foundation for a viable long-term ecosystem supporting EIRENE RI operators.

Below we provide major **advantages of EIRENE ERIC establishment**:

USER Experience	Establishment of the Single access point for distributed services and simplified application and approval process Consistent service quality across the RIs (QA/QC), integrated work-flows, established SOPs and enhanced support for cross-facility research projects
Costs, organisation, governance	Pooling of resources, increased number of users reducing unit costs Reduced duplication – decreasing investment costs Economies of scale and scope, VAT exemptions Coordinated funding strategies and budget allocation Unified decision-making processes across distributed facilities Standardized policies and procedures for consistent operations Streamlined administrative oversight and accountability Professional centralised supporting and administrative services
Operational efficiency	Interoperability standards ensuring seamless data/material/service exchange Harmonized protocols for user access and service delivery Centralized performance monitoring and evaluation Coordinated maintenance and technology upgrades
Strategic benefits and sustainability	Increased international visibility and credibility, stronger positioning globally Eligibility for specific funding opportunities, alignment with EU research priorities Unified voice in policy discussions and strategic planning Long term financial planning and stability – national support
Data management and data access	Definitions and harmonization of data management practices, centralized repositories or/and clearly defined policies and processes Single entry point to data, high visibility of data facilities High visibility of data, easier outreach to target groups
Internationalization	Enhanced visibility and joint outreach efforts Joint stakeholder engagement strategies, staff-exchange programmes

8 Governance structures of EIRENE

EIRENE aims to submit the ERIC application within its implementation phase. The final structure of EIRENE-ERIC (Figure 4) is designed to be simple and clear. Notably, the distinction between what is or is not included in the ERIC is distinctly defined (in orange). The governance structure is dictated mostly by the ERIC legal framework.

Figure 1 – EIRENE-ERIC Final Structure

The **General Assembly** will be the highest governing body of EIRENE and the ultimate decision-making body comprising of delegates of EIRENE members and observers responsible for EIRENE's overall direction and supervision. The General Assembly will consist of the country representatives of the former Funders Forum.

The **Director-General**, appointed by the General Assembly, will be the legal representative of EIRENE-ERIC, responsible for all its activities. The term of the Director General shall be five years and may be renewed once by the GA. The DG shall be based in the statutory seat of EIRENE-ERIC and shall be responsible for managing the Head Office staff, Central Coordination Units, and other activities of EIRENE-ERIC. In the interim period, the EIRENE Coordinator – prof. Jana Klánová takes these responsibilities.

The EIRENE-ERIC **Head Office** will be responsible for the operational management of EIRENE-ERIC and supporting all its functions and will be located at the statutory seat of the EIRENE-ERIC in the Czech Republic. In the interim period, the EIRENE Coordination Team handles tasks that the Head Office until EIRENE-ERIC is established.

EIRENE-ERIC will deliver services across six key domains: Chemical Profiling, Toxicological Profiling, Biological Profiling, Environmental Samples & Data, Human Samples & Data, and Tools. Each service domain will be managed at the EIRENE-ERIC level by a **Central Coordination Unit** and hosted within the EIRENE Head Office or by a Member State. **National Nodes** will represent the research service providers in Member States. EIRENE will utilize the **advisory bodies**, Scientific Advisory Board, Ethics Advisory Board and the Stakeholder Forum.

9 EIRENE Service Pillars and Technical Design

The scientific vision and the scope of capacities for exposomics to be developed and/or integrated were defined in the preparatory phase of the EIRENE project (2022-2025). These include mobilising existing large-scale **geospatial and satellite data** to be used for the characterisation of external exposures. To construct detailed (personal) external exposure profiles of target populations, they should be combined with advanced tools (**micro-samplers and wearable sensor technologies for continuous monitoring**) collecting high-resolution spatial and temporal data in real time. Harmonised characterisation of internal exposures requires **high-throughput infrastructural platforms integrating state-of-the-art mass spectrometry with AI-driven analytical tools** addressing the extensive spectrum of exogenous exposure markers, including chemicals of concern, and endogenous effect markers. The toxicity of chemical mixtures found in biological tissues must be evaluated using **innovative hazard characterisation and toxicity testing platforms**, including high throughput platforms employing New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for testing the safety of chemicals, and exposure simulation chambers. This provides data for the development of **Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs)** improving mechanistic understanding of biological responses and **next-generation risk assessment tools** integrating exposure and hazard data into predictive models that better capture the complexity of real-world exposures. A wide spectrum of exogenous (exposure) and endogenous (effect) markers identified in high-resolution data from emerging mass-spec technologies enable the assessment of associations between exposures and effects. These technologies - when harmonised and employed in systematic population studies where their results can be combined with additional external exposure data (**natural, built-in, and social environments, occupation, lifestyle, diet**), **genomic** (and other *-omic*) data and **longitudinal clinical/health records** - can significantly advance our mechanistic understanding of disease development and identify factors playing major roles in this process.

To achieve the EIRENE objectives and ambitions and enable challenge-driven research linking environmental factors to human health, we need to integrate necessary capacities in the multi-dimensional infrastructural matrix consisting of (i) **longitudinal observation cohorts** (birth, child, adult, occupational, ageing), **cross-cutting biomonitoring and health surveys, and clinical studies** (including biobanks); **harmonised experimental capacities and leading-edge innovative technologies** to assess (ii) **internal exposures** and their biological effects, (iii) **external environmental exposures** by combining personal sensors with monitoring and satellite data, (iv) **hazards** and (v) **risks** associated with toxic chemicals and their mixtures, as well as (vi) research **environments for integrating** individual-level clinical, environmental and social datasets with geospatial data, advanced models and data interpretation tools (including tools for the safe governance and management of sensitive data, their harmonisation, and federated analyses) bridging disciplinary divides and providing integrated services to empower European research linking environmental exposures to human health (Figure 1).

Figure 1: EIRENE ambitions (right) and domains of necessary infrastructural capacities: population studies (left), experimental, technological and computational capacities for internal and external exposure, hazard and risk assessment (bottom), and research environments and tools for data integration and interpretation (top)

Roadmap to successful implementation

In the preparatory phase, the EIRENE consortium focused on formulation of the scientific challenges, identification of associated research capacity needs and mapping existing service capacities in the EIRENE consortium. This resulted in a detailed map of capacities available across the EIRENE national nodes describing also their readiness, quality and development strategy. The services ready to be provided via the centralised EIRENE open access system at the beginning of the implementation period were identified.

Following steps define the roadmap for the EIRENE implementation period.

1.1. EIRENE Catalogue of services

Available services will be clustered according to the EIRENE service pillars and organised in the service catalogue. On-going efforts of the PARC Partnership (e.g. existing Chemical Risk Assessment Knowledge Hub, CRA KH) will be leveraged: The CRA KH mapping laboratory capacities, monitoring and biomonitoring efforts, data and tools will be enhanced and upgraded to provide information on availability of services. The catalogue will enable registering services of other collaborating RIs and will be regularly updated.

1.1.1. Laboratory services

Special attention will be paid to a proper documentation, quality assurance procedures and compliance with Open Science (availability of SOPs, libraries, data-processing tools etc.) as a base for future harmonisation and upscaling.

1.1.2. Cohort catalogue

Similarly, a simple catalogue of available cohorts will be developed to serve globally for future harmonisation and collaborative projects. The synergy with the IHEN project will be exploited.

1.2. EIRENE service access and management system (single-point access)

To provide access to EIRENE services, the access management system will be fully developed together with the Service access policy. It will allow the registration of all relevant distributed facilities and services listed in the catalogue, matchmaking of applicants to service providers, submission of proposals, support the evaluation process, and implement committee-controlled access to the selected facilities and services including exchange of contracts, monitoring and reporting. The development of the EIRENE catalogue of services and open access management system will be the most important goal for the first year of the Implementation period. This effort will be supported by synergistic projects, namely the Teaming project with EIRENE and existing and new INFRA-DEV and INFRA-SERV projects.

1.3. Providing physical, remote and virtual access to EIRENE services

The core principles for providing access to EIRENE services include (i) prioritisation for access being based on scientific merit and technical feasibility (in case of multiple high-quality proposals, the preference is given to new RI users), (ii) making all meta(data) FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), and (iii) Users retain ownership of their intellectual property rights. The Service access policy will define the process for establishment of the User Selection Committee to review applications for access, and the Panel of Expert Reviewers, and establishment of the evaluation criteria. First call offering EIRENE open-access services is expected in the second year of the EIRENE implementation.

1.4. Integrating services of other RI from the ESFRI landscape and relevant projects

The open-access system will enable providing a single-point access to services of multiple research infrastructures from the ESFRI landscape but also capacities developed in the synergistic international projects (PARC, IHEN, NEXUS etc.). Special attention will be paid to the development of integrated service and integrated knowledge access. A combination of exposure data with population surveys or clinical trials has a potential to advance health and ageing research in Europe and provide deeper insights into disease aetiology, progression, and treatment response. A translation of data on environmental exposures to knowledge and advice needed for informed policy making and/or decision making in clinical practice will be also pursued. The new INFRA-SERV and INFRA-TECH project opportunities will be leveraged to promote such synergies.

1.5. Increasing quality, integrity and openness of research methods and data

EIRENE will continuously enhance the quality and capacity of its infrastructural services while laying the groundwork for innovative solutions to emerging challenges. For example, there is a great need for the development of novel screening methods and the large-scale assessment of human exposure to anthropogenic chemicals. High-throughput procedures will be advanced to rationalise sample preparation and expand suspect and non-targeted screening. A unified framework, based on cutting-edge high-resolution mass spectrometry, will support harmonised chemical profiling of human biosamples to identify biomarkers of exposure and effect. Unlike prior single-site successes (e.g., Olympic Drug Testing Labs, International Phenome Centres), multi-site harmonisation has been hindered by diverse platforms and protocols. Uniquely, EIRENE partners have automated operations, standardised system suitability assessments, and will implement multi-site harmonisation and iterate concordance testing to achieve distributed replication. Robust QA/QC procedures will underpin the transnational deployment of integrated targeted,

suspect, and non-targeted analyses, extending the characterisation of internalised exposures and biological responses. Data storage and processing are equally critical for the annotation, identification, and quantification of measured chemicals. While existing tools can extract and identify mass spectral features, most do not enable full reproducibility of results. The Galaxy platform was developed specifically to ease the access and use of software for scientists, providing fully reproducible FAIR data analysis and reporting. However, current tools for processing mass spectrometry data are disconnected, and unable to be leveraged in a reusable, modular manner. In partnership with ELIXIR and EBI, EIRENE will extend standardised metadata models, and upgrade workflows to become a modular suite of Galaxy tools with interoperable inputs and outputs, reaching a European standard for processing of data from chemical profiling of human biosamples that is fully compliant with international harmonisation, sustainability, and FAIR objectives. Launching these methods in high-throughput facilities will enable a new generation of large-scale studies focused on a better understanding of the impact of various factors on the onset and development of diseases. Such infrastructural capacity will then be applied to screen the sets of well-designed and harmonized cohort studies to ensure adequate statistical power needed for the health impact assessment of combined exposures.

1.6. Alignment with the FAIR principles

Improved data sharing and integration between various human and environmental studies is another important challenge addressing which would enable the joint interpretation of data across various disciplines and the development of new prediction models, prevention, and intervention strategies. In EIRENE, we will provide a roadmap on data FAIRification and orchestration needed to operationalize current and future physical, remote and virtual access services. However, we will also showcase an exposome data integration to demonstrate the workflow from FAIR data to knowledge for policymakers, focusing on integrating health observation and health data for risk assessment. The outcomes of such efforts will be available to both the scientific community and policymakers to inform evidence-based decision-making for the adequate protection of human health and better healthcare.

1.7. Standards and ontologies

EIRENE data and metadata models will be designed for interoperability and will be openly accessible whenever possible. Host organisations will be able to determine the level of data access (open, registered, and controlled), which will then be set up in cooperation with e.g., the ELIXIR Beacon Network. Inspired by GA4GH, this will provide convenient access and compatibility across institutions/ERICs/National Nodes. 'Access tiers' will define precise authorization requirements. For example, 'open access' Beacons are accessible to anonymous internet users, whereas 'registered access' Beacons are accessible only to registered users who have agreed to a set of data use conditions. To facilitate interoperability, the same metadata standards, data standards, vocabularies, and other FAIR Enabling Resources will be used across all EIRENE domains, as much as possible. However, the specific needs of each research domain may require the use of specific solutions for FAIRification. The data strategy will develop recommendations for standards, vocabularies and other FAIR Enabling Resources to be used across EIRENE. For instance, for the reporting of toxicological omics data, the guidelines of the OECD's Extended Advisory Group of Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics will be considered.

1.8. Open Science practices

Open science is premised upon broad access to scientific knowledge, tools, data, and publications. It promotes accurate verification of scientific results, reduces duplicities, and increases efficiency,

productivity, cost-effectiveness, collaboration, innovation, and trust in science. The EIRENE consortium exemplify Open Science, by integrating previously scattered capacities into a cohesive, widely accessible and efficient network of open services. It will bring complementary research capacities from across and beyond Europe together to provide excellent services necessary to advance exposome research. Specific attention will be paid to developing harmonised methodologies, quality assurance and quality control mechanisms as well as analytical and data processing frameworks and reporting standards. Adoption of FAIR Data practices and compliance with EOSC is emphasised, describing the development of the EIRENE framework for collection, curation, harmonisation, and interpretation of data and providing access to them in support of the European Open Science. The open-access guidelines and policies will be available to potential users via the SIRENE web page. Synergies with the European Open Science, European Health Data Space and other European data related efforts will be reinforced.

1.9. Open data

We will develop and offer the main entry point to the SIRENE data sources for registered users at the SIRENE webpage (partner's web pages). A user-friendly web interface, including search tools and relevant criteria, will be developed to search in the metadata catalogues of all SIRENE domains. It will maintain the metadata catalogues and the links to the original storage place of specific data, as well as tools for data analysis. The access platform will host all services necessary for managing and executing workflows, including dashboards for private computational environments deployed on-demand by users. Open-source codes for data processing and dataset submission/annotation will be reinforced as well.

1.10. Development of new technologies

EIRENE triggers the development of new methods and technologies in many related areas including automatization and miniaturisation of analytical procedures to increase sensitivity and selectivity of high-resolution screening, new advancements in personal sampling and sensing technologies, new methodologies for non-animal toxicological testing but especially new generative AI tools for integrating and interpreting multidimensional data. The unique core facilities will not only provide access to excellent research capacities, often unavailable at the national level, but also support the development of a creative environment fostering innovations in the EU and beyond.

10 EIRENE RI User Support Strategy

The EIRENE user strategy follows a dynamic and iterative cycle to ensure continuous adaptation and user engagement. Based on experiences of other RIs the role of outreach, feedback, and service optimization in enhancing the infrastructure's accessibility and effectiveness.

The strategy cycle consists of five stages (Figure 2):

1. **Outreach and acquisition:** Engaging target user communities through tailored communication campaigns, workshops, and conferences to raise awareness of EIRENE's services.
2. **Understanding user needs:** Conducting surveys, stakeholder consultations, and pilot testing to gather insights on evolving user demands and refine service offerings.
3. **Service delivery and experience:** Providing high-quality access to exposome data platforms, analytical tools, and training programs, ensuring seamless user interactions.
4. **Feedback and optimization:** Establishing structured mechanisms to collect user feedback and drive iterative improvements in service quality and accessibility.
5. **Expansion and refinement:** Using insights from pilot users to scale service offerings, optimize access systems, and strengthen user support mechanisms.

This strategy cycle ensures that EIRENE remains user-centered, adaptable, and aligned with real-world research and policy needs. By integrating structured feedback loops, performance monitoring, and stakeholder engagement strategies, EIRENE will foster long-term sustainability, innovation, and collaboration within the exposome research community.

Figure 2 Schematic presentation of the user strategy cycle

In designing the access framework, existing processes from other ESFRI research infrastructures and national facilities have been examined to ensure alignment with best practices. The framework encompasses the full user access lifecycle, including entry points, application and evaluation processes, assessment criteria, funding mechanisms, and acknowledgment policies. Additionally, it defines the necessary documentation and IT tools required for implementation, as well as the executive and decision-making bodies responsible for overseeing user access.

To inform the development of a user-focused infrastructure, EIRENE PPP organized two online user strategy workshops in April 2025. These workshops targeted potential users, including representatives from government agencies, regulatory bodies, research institutions, NGOs, and policy support organizations. Each session included presentations and interactive discussions using Mentimeter, enabling participants to express priorities and expectations.

Key findings from the workshops include:

- **Strong demand for cloud-based services and remote access tools** to facilitate efficient and decentralized exposome research.
- **High value placed on data interpretation support**, with many participants emphasizing the need for EIRENE to offer analytical guidance and standardized workflows.
- **Preferred communication channels** included the EIRENE website, targeted newsletters, and structured webinars. Email updates and live Q&A sessions were also suggested for real-time engagement.
- Participants emphasized the **importance of training**, particularly through webinars, physical access workshops, and modular, step-by-step documentation. There was also interest in hands-on training in laboratories and with wearable monitoring devices.
- **Live updates on analytical protocols**, a user forum, and regular feedback loops were proposed as mechanisms to strengthen community engagement and knowledge exchange.
- **Policy-driven organizations** were highlighted as priority stakeholders requiring tailored access and interpretive support.
- Although no new service types were explicitly requested, participants noted that **additional needs would likely emerge** as the infrastructure becomes operational, reinforcing the need for a flexible and adaptive support model.

As EIRENE progressed through the Preparatory Phase, a set of recommendations has been developed to ensure an effective, inclusive, and adaptable user strategy. The work during EIRENE PPP emphasizes the importance of proactive engagement, structured access mechanisms, and impact assessment (Table below).

- **Broad user engagement:** Implement tailored communication strategies to reach scientific, private, and public-sector audiences.
- **Building trust and relationships:** Foster transparent interactions with users to ensure inclusivity and long-term engagement.
- **Monitoring of evolving user needs:** Use pilot studies and structured feedback mechanisms to continuously adapt services and tools.
- **Documentation and performance tracking:** Maintain detailed records of user access and service utilization to evaluate impact and optimize workflows.
- **Open access commitment:** Ensure services are guided by FAIR principles, promoting scientific progress and data sharing.
- **Stakeholder alignment:** Establish partnerships with policymakers, industry/business, and NGOs to strengthen EIRENE's impact and sustainability.
- **KPI-based performance evaluation:** Apply indicators from D8.3 to monitor user satisfaction, service efficiency, and research impact.

Our recent findings emphasize the importance of stakeholder engagement in refining EIRENE's infrastructure. Training programs and structured onboarding processes will facilitate the seamless adoption of EIRENE's tools and services across various user groups.

Table 1 Recommendations for EIRENE user strategy

Recommendations for EIRENE User Strategy	Details	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
Broad user engagement	EIRENE should strive to reach diverse target audiences within the scientific, private, and public sectors through conferences, training and social media.	Number of new user registrations, diversity of user demographics, and engagement in outreach events.
Building trust and relationships	Foster strong, transparent relationships with users to ensure they feel supported and valued.	User satisfaction scores, number of returning users, and feedback on transparency and support.
Monitoring evolving user needs	Continuously track user feedback and anticipate emerging needs, especially for innovative services and technological tools.	Frequency of user surveys, number of feature requests, and adaptation rate of new services.
Documentation and statistics	Maintain detailed records of user access and service utilization to track EIRENE's impact and relevance to its community.	Volume of data access logs, user activity tracking, and service utilization trends.
Proactive user feedback response	Analyse feedback efficiently and publicly communicate actions taken to maintain transparency and trust.	Average response time to user feedback, percentage of resolved issues, and transparency reports.
Service catalogue updates	Regularly update the EIRENE service catalogue to keep users informed of new opportunities and tools.	Frequency of service catalogue updates, user awareness of new services, and usage statistics.
Open access commitment	Ensure open access to services guided by principles promoting scientific progress, data sharing, and collaboration.	Percentage of services available as open access, citation rate of EIRENE tools and data.
User-centric approach	Prioritize the needs of the user community in the design, implementation, and expansion of services.	User retention rate, usability scores, and direct user contributions to service development.
Stakeholder alignment	Integrate stakeholder engagement strategies from D8.2 to build robust partnerships with policymakers, industry/business, and NGOs.	Number of stakeholder partnerships, level of policy integration, and collaborative project outputs.
KPIs for performance tracking	Leverage KPIs from D8.3 to monitor user satisfaction, service efficiency, and infrastructure impact.	Service performance benchmarks, user experience ratings, and infrastructure efficiency metrics.

11 Human Resources, Education and Training

The sustainability of EIRENE RI is dependent on well-defined personnel requirements i.e. competence maps and staffing. This in turn will require an organizational structure for EIRENE RI that includes the national node members. It is likely that we are discussing more than 60 individual partners contributing to the RI. The structures of the national nodes are dependent on national requirements and conditions. However, the node members are to act both nationally and at the level of EIRENE RI. This depends on national vs. international stakeholders, but the offerings should be as similar as possible to allow stakeholders to access EIRENE RI.

The HR strategy needs to be aligned with the vision and strategic objectives of EIRENE. By developing and implementing a HR strategy, EIRENE RI can effectively develop and leverage its human capital to achieve its mission of advancing exposome research in Europe and effectively addressing environmental determinants of health. At the same time, the HR strategy needs to remain flexible enough to accommodate evolving needs and priorities of EIRENE RI.

The following aspects have been evaluated as most important from an EIRENE perspective, based on the current state as well as future needs.

EIRENE RI and national RI node organization

The national node organization needs to be specified to be able to evaluate how it influences the HR principles in EIRENE RI. HR may be influenced by their national role versus their roles in EIRENE RI. Any such differences need to be clarified in the strategy plan.

Staffing plan

Perform regular and comprehensive HR inventories and forecasting to understand the current and future HR needs of EIRENE RI. This includes assessing FTE, expertise, skills, and educational levels required for different services within the RI. These inventories should be updated biannually.

Career and competence development

Identify programs for capacity building and skill enhancement to meet the evolving needs of EIRENE RI. This includes identifying training opportunities for personnel to acquire new skills and expertise required for advanced technologies and services, promote collaborative partnerships and knowledge sharing, and strengthen collaborative partnerships among national nodes and institutions to facilitate knowledge sharing and exchange of best practices. This can enhance synergies, improve access to resources, and mitigate risks associated with resource concentration. The RI should develop plans for connecting partners.

Diversification of expertise

Encourage diversification of expertise within EIRENE RI to ensure a holistic approach to environmental exposure assessment. This includes addressing any identified weaknesses and promoting interdisciplinary collaboration.

HR principles are based on transparency and equality

Uphold principles of transparency, respect, equality, and cooperation in all HR practices within EIRENE RI. This includes promoting diversity and inclusion in recruitment and career development opportunities.

Staffing plan

The staffing plan will be further developed within the EIRENE Implementation phase (and EIRENE Implementation project). However, thanks to the above presented questionnaire and its results and the planning for the EIRENE ERIC Head Office and CCUs resources, there is basic plan and needs already

defined. For the Head office, the plan is clear in terms of positions, and also in terms of the FTEs needed in next five years according to the activity and financial plan.

Staffing plan of EIRENE ERIC Head office

Based on the expected roles of the EIRENE ERIC Head Office, we present the corresponding positions to answer the needs. Since the plan is developed for 5-Years, the development of FTEs is planned correspondingly. The positions are:

- Scientific director
- CEO
- Manager
- Open Access Manager
- Financial manager
- Project manager
- HR manager
- PR & communication
- ELSI specialist
- QA/QC / Accreditation expert
- Data specialist

For all the positions there will be the open international call following the EIRENE RI HR policy and namely to attract the talents and expertise from all around Europe. For that, we also expect the conditions to be fully competitive at the international scale. The expected FTEs are provided below.

Table 2 EIRENE ERIC Head Office positions - FTEs in 5Y

	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Scientific director	1	1	1	1	1
CEO	0,5	1	1	1	1
Manager	0,5	0,5	0,5	1	1
Open Access Manager	0,5	0,75	0,75	1	1
Financial manager	1	1	1	1	1
Project manager	0,5	1	1	2	2
HR manager	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
PR & communication	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
ELSI specialist	0,5	0,5	1	1	1
QA/QC / Accreditation expert	0,75	1	1	1	1
Data specialist	1	1	1	1	1
TOTAL	7,25	8,75	9,25	11	11

Staffing plan of EIRENE ERIC CCUs

As described in the Del. 5.3 we expect there will be the Central Coordination Units in different domains crucial for the EIRENE RI Service provision. Currently, two CCUs are already designed with its basic roles – the staffing has been planned correspondingly. Below we provide the staffing plan for the CCU – EIRENE RI Reference Laboratory and EIRENE RI Data Center – both planned to be in the Czech Republic. The other CCUs' roles are being developed and planned.

Table 3 EIRENE ERIC CCU positions - average FTEs in 5Y

EIRENE Reference laboratory	exp. FTE
Senior scientific leader	1
Research specialist	2
Laboratory specialist	3
QA/QC specialist	1
TOTAL	7

EIRENE Data center (CZ)	exp. FTE
Senior scientific leader	1
Senior programmer	2
System architect	3
Programmer	1
Data analyst	1
ICT administrator	1
TOTAL	9

For the EIRENE ERIC Head Office and the CCUs the staffing plan is relatively clear and will be confirmed by the General Assembly when approving the EIRENE ERIC Statutes.

Staffing plan of EIRENE National Nodes

The staffing plans for national nodes are continuously being updated and follow the logic presented in specific document. Next figure 6 presents which positions and in which countries (Nodes) the capacities shall be increased. We have gathered detailed information, which specific positions and in which national nodes (institution within the nodes) plan to increase the capacities. In this sense, there is clear plan – description of positions, expected timing, institutional hiring and HR policies etc.

Figure 3 Human resources (full-time equivalents, FTE) in EIRENE RI, divided into different services offered and the % of expertise the institutions are planning to increase the FTE the coming five years.

The increases are expected in following positions:

- Administrative staff
- AI researcher
- Analytical chemist
- Bioinformatician
- Data analyst
- Data engineer
- Data manager
- Epidemiologist
- IT support
- Lab assistant
- Lab assistant / technical staff
- Nurse
- Other

Training strategy

The training strategy will aim at establishing an EIRENE training network as a tool for the education and training of excellent scientists, a new generation of RI operators and technicians, as well as service managers. The ambition is to provide excellence in EIRENE but also extend to external networks and interested parties, as well as large scale projects both in Europe and globally.

The primary target group for the training strategy is the **internal staff members**, that is EIRENE partners providing services in EIRENE. This target group is the core foundation of providing services and excellence in science and management to provide for the needs of stakeholders. The secondary target group is **external communities**, for which the EIRENE training network is made available to educate scientists outside EIRENE, stakeholders and the public in the art of the core services as well as knowledge on environmental and human health.

To establish a network of harmonized laboratories, databases, and data processing tools, it is crucial to prioritize workshops and internships where the EIRENE staff meet and share knowledge. These workshops should be designed specifically for internal purposes, rather than for external participants. Internships are particularly crucial—they are the first and most important step in building our internal capacity by letting early-career researchers work together across countries and disciplines, fostering collaboration and innovation in the lab. Summer schools, in collaboration with larger projects like PARC, are also part of the EIRENE strategy. The training efforts should first-hand take advantage of the institutional offerings and competencies for hosting the efforts. In order to promote the competence provision development academia should prepare an inventory of available study programs for EIRENE partner professionals. At a later stage, digital courses should be developed to further support learning and training.

Research infrastructures exist to support excellent science, which requires ongoing investment in cutting-edge technologies. However, it is equally important to continuously educate the staff. Embedded continuous education needs to be included in the structure of each service and competence centres of EIRENE. Annual physical meetings among the different competence centres will promote teambuilding and competence exchange. This needs to be identified at the respective centres on a regular basis and includes ensuring that, alongside reinvestment plans for instruments, there is a Human Resources Development Plan for technicians and researchers. Equally important are the tools for enhancing management skills among research infrastructure managers such as the program in Milan is an Executive Masters (MBA) in Management of Research Infrastructures (<https://emmri.unimib.it/>). Education from other organisations may also be considered, e.g. the European Organization of Research Managers, and Open Access Managers.

Training should be coordinated at the central level in connection with the quality of the overall infrastructure. This means that the coordination of training activities will be one of the key services managed centrally by EIRENE. An operational committee or steering group, comprising representatives from various competence centres and services of EIRENE, will oversee these activities. Forming a competence centre on education and training should be considered. A clear description of how this effort will be organized, where it will fit within the coordination structure, how it will be implemented in the short term, who will be involved, and how it will be communicated, is to be performed by the EIRENE coordinator.

In the short term, the analysis of the needs assessment shows that data handling, closely linked to data generation, is the main training gap within EIRENE. This should be prioritized, and already existing training networks and university connections needs to be identified by the EIRENE competence centre on data handling. It remains to be investigated which are the relevant staff groups that need to be addressed, for example technicians or data analysts. The most efficient way to determine where the training of internal staff members should be performed using existing training offerings needs to be

elucidated. Critical trainings that are not in the existing EIRENE RI needs to be identified, such as trainings in management of a research infrastructure.

In the long term, elements to develop and possibly offer as a paid service for external parties need to be identified as well as setting up a business model for the ETN. This could include offering online courses for free to generate greater societal impact, particularly for low-income countries. Additionally, minimize overlap with other infrastructures, organizations, and projects like PARC, by fostering cooperation and networking is needed. It is recognized that this effort is focused on building the EIRENE internal capacity for providing services and that the survey has garnered more responses from the scientific community than from the service providers since currently, only a small number of the EIRENE partners have Open Access facilities providing these services. Next step is to present the strategy to stakeholders and user community for input to verify that our training and development meets the expectation of the receivers of the EIRENE services.

The EIRENE survey identified significant training needs, particularly in data generation and data handling, which together accounted for 66% of the reported needs. The results also highlighted that general training and training related to health and the environment were less prominent but still important. This suggests that EIRENE must prioritize training in these critical areas to address the identified gaps. The most preferred training formats identified were digital courses, workshops, and summer schools. These formats are favoured due to their flexibility and dynamic content, which contrasts with the lack of interest in more rigid academic courses like MSc or PhD programs. This indicates a need for more accessible and adaptable training opportunities within EIRENE. Although there is some overlap between the current training offerings and the identified needs, there is an indication that a better alignment between what is offered and what is needed, is required.

The EIRENE training strategy emphasizes building internal capacity, particularly through workshops, internships, and continuous education tailored for EIRENE staff. This includes developing a harmonized network of laboratories and databases through EIRENE competence centres. In the long term, EIRENE aims to extend its training offerings to external participants and possibly monetize some services, while also ensuring cooperation with international projects and infrastructures, thus minimizing overlaps.

12 Communication plan

Communication activities of EIRENE RI target both the internal and external target groups. Internal communication is very important since the EIRENE RI is a distributed research infrastructure and the number of partners is relatively high. External target groups are much broader and diverse. As such, the ambitions of the communication strategy towards the audience outside the EIRENE RI are namely to

- **increase awareness** – key players and external stakeholders are informed to fortify the position of EIRENE on the “map” or research infrastructures,
- **draw attention** of scientific and user community,
- **actively engage** national governments, regional authorities, and other public and private funders,
- **enhance the reputation and visibility** of the EIRENE RI and its partners at the local, national, and international levels, and given the current state of EIRENE,
- to certain extent **exploit the research results and outcomes** and
- **generate a demand** for services developed and offered. Crucial is also the communication with the management of the PARC partnership, and IHEN and EHEN clusters, which associate the exposome related projects and the outcome of which should potentially be hosted by EIRENE.

Our key communication messages presented are:

- **EIRENE provides outstanding services enabling conducting of the excellent science in environmental health sciences and *exposomics***
- **EIRENE offers an open access to available regional capacities**, and a top expertise supporting research, innovation, and capacity building globally.
- **EIRENE builds a community** of researchers, RI operators and users, cooperate on the development of new services, and provide professional training for the users and our professional staff.
- **EIRENE is socially responsible**; we support the implementation of the global treaties protecting the environment and human health and translate research results into policy documents and applications.

Communication activities are integrated in all EIRENE RI-related activities. They include not only a continuous communication with the target audiences but also an establishment and maintenance of the relations with stakeholders (including the national governments, ESFRI, European Commission). To ensure the effective communication, the target audience and appropriate dissemination channels were carefully identified as every target group responds differently to specific dissemination channels. That is why the detailed plan was developed based on the target groups’ needs.

Table 4 Target groups

	Target groups
INTERNAL	General Assembly National Stakeholders National Nodes and Hubs Internal Scientific and Technical Community

EXTERNAL	Scientific community Technology Community RI Community Policy makers (EU, EU DGs, National policy makers, Regional Agencies, EU Institutions – EP, EC NCPs, Funding Agencies, European Agencies) International Agencies (WHO, UN agencies) Industry (Companies in relevant area, Manufacturers, SMEs, Clusters and Associations) Investors Project partners General Public (Universities, Schools, Press, Social Networks) EOSC ESFRI
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13 Monitoring and evaluation

The EIRENE RI KPIs are being developed based on the Report of the ESFRI Working Group on monitoring RIs performance ([ESFRI Working Group, 2019](#)). The intention is to monitor the KPIs at the level of the core facilities, summarise the results per country and/or pillar and present the results in a report. An initial set of KPIs is being proposed for further discussion. The final set for evaluations during of the implementation and operational phases will be proposed by the EIRENE RI management and is to be approved by the General Assembly in the future.

The proposed set of KPIs is an initial set that will be subject to change in the future. They will be slightly more high level than what would ideally be required because the objectives of EIRENE are also still high level at this point and the activities to fulfil those objectives are not worked out. Therefore, it will be difficult to determine the method of calculation and define the required data for the KPIs. This will have to be reevaluated and adapted where necessary when more information becomes available throughout the current Preparatory Phase Project.

The set of KPIs should allow to monitor of the progress of EIRENE and to inform about its performance. It is necessary to distinguish from the socio-economic assessment, which is completely different exercise. The main objectives of EIRENE RI which, the progress and achievement of which will be monitored, are provided below:

- Enabling scientific excellence
- Delivery of education and training and enable knowledge transfer
- Enhancing collaboration in Europe
- Facilitating economic activities
- Outreach to the public
- Providing scientific data and associated services
- Providing scientific support/advice (to policy)
- Facilitating international cooperation
- Fostering innovation

Key performance indicators

In 2019 the working group of ESFRI on the development of a common approach across RIs to **monitor performance** based on **KPIs** published a comprehensive framework of KPIs that can be adopted by RIs and adapted where needed to fit their specific needs. The KPIs were developed to address the most common objectives of pan-European RIs and to increase the usefulness and relevance for the widest ranges of RIs. Key reasons on why to adopt KPIs according to ERICs is to have an internal management tool to achieve tangible results and enable monitoring of progression, to document developments and improvements, to have an instrument to communicate successes, to improve the chances for long-term impact and value, to be able to mitigate risks as problems can be detected early and lastly, to measure the level of engagement with each national node.

KPIs are the most used method to monitor progress towards objectives but they are often poor proxies of progression. The WG therefore suggests a shift towards including narratives and context to accompany the adopted KPIs. It is very important to realise that the ESFRI KPI framework is meant as a supporting tool for RIs and it is not meant to be adopted integrally. RIs should evaluate their objectives and which data can be gathered and then propose, evaluate and adopt relevant KPIs.

The WG has made some practical recommendations:

- A reference sheet with a definition, data sources, method of calculation and other relevant information regarding the calculation or applicability should be created for each KPI,
- Quantitative KPIs should be accompanied with a short narrative that describes the specific context of the KPI,

- Specific methods or tools to collect data in order to reliably report on the indicators need to be developed or agreed by RIs,
- Qualitative indicators should be used in addition to quantitative indicators to present the progress towards the objectives,
- Collect data and periodically calculate KPIs and make this available for consultations in the future.

The WG identified the objectives with the highest relevance for the most RIs in general whereby at least 40% of all ERICs share the objective. Nine such objectives were identified of which the first one was shared by all ERICs: (1) enabling scientific excellence, (2) delivery of education and training, (3) enhancing transnational collaboration in Europe, (4) facilitating economic activity, (5) outreach to the public, (6) optimising data use, (7) provision of scientific advice, (8) facilitating international co-operation and (9) optimising management. A set of 21 KPIs were developed which complied with the RACER criteria. Certain indicators that did not comply with the RACER criteria were regarded as valuable additions to the KPIs and were formed into narratives. As mentioned earlier not all of these objectives and KPIs are relevant for every RI either at their current phase or never. Also, some might not be relevant in their current form and require adaptation to become relevant.

Preliminary KPIs for EIRENE RI

As mentioned above, the proposed set of KPIs is a preliminary set. The final set of KPIs for EIRENE RI will be proposed by EIRENE RI management and approved by the General Assembly in the future. As noted earlier, to be able to develop a project's KPIs, objectives need to be clear. Listing the objectives of EIRENE RI (see above) was the first course of action in the development of the KPIs. We then used the ESFRI Working Group report on 'Monitoring of Research Infrastructures Performance' as the basis and complemented that with the OECD report on the reference framework for assessing the scientific and socio-economic impact of research infrastructures (albeit noted that the OECD report is partially on impact which in general is not part of KPIs). Additionally, we identified some KPIs from BBMRI-ERIC that might be interesting for EIRENE RI. Most of the objectives identified in the ESFRI report match the objectives of EIRENE RI. The corresponding KPIs may therefore also be applicable to EIRENE RI. OECD identified some additional KPIs that may correspond to the objectives of EIRENE RI. We made a list of the objectives and related KPIs in Table 5. At this stage the specifics and details of the internal working of EIRENE RI are not worked out. The relevance and feasibility of the proposed KPIs (will the required data be available?) remains to be evaluated once the operations of EIRENE RI are clearer. This also means that we cannot really give a detailed methodology for the calculation of the indicators at this moment. For the indicators described in the ESFRI report, we can take the reference sheets as a basis and adapt where needed.

Table 5: Proposition of preliminary set of KPIs for EIRENE RI (1,8). The cursive KPIs are based on some KPIs from BBMRI-ERIC and adapted to the context of EIRENE RI.

EIRENE RI Objective	Proposed preliminary KPIs
<i>Enabling scientific excellence</i>	Number of user requests for access
	Number of users served
	Number of user requests
	Number of publications
	Number of citations
	Percentage of top (10%) cited publications
	<i>Ratio of number of services delivered and total number of services available in the network</i>
	<i>Average ratio of number of services on number of infrastructures</i>
<i>Delivery of education and training and enable knowledge transfer</i>	Number of master and PhD students using the RI
	Total number of trained non-RI staff
	Number of scientific conferences, seminars, webinars, ... organised by the RI
	Number of educational and outreach activities
	Number of participants in educational and outreach activities
<i>Enhancing collaboration in Europe</i>	Number of members of the RI from ESFRI countries
	Share of users and publication per ESFRI member country
<i>Facilitating economic activities</i>	Income from commercial activities and the number of entities paying for service
	Number of regional firms using the RI (can be categorized by size/turnover)
	Number of suppliers (local/regional) (may also add turnover data)
<i>Outreach to the public</i>	Engagement achieved by direct contact
	Outreach through media
	Outreach via the RIs own web and social media
<i>Providing scientific data and associated services</i>	Number of publicly available curated data sets used externally
	Number of data requests
	<i>Facilities connected to IT services</i>
<i>Providing scientific support/advice (to policy)</i>	Participation by RIs in policy related activities
	Citations in policy related publications
	Number of resources (data, specimen, informatics) dedicated to support policy
<i>Facilitating international cooperation</i>	Share of users and publications per non-ESFRI member country
	International trainees
	Number of members of the RI from non-ESFRI countries
<i>Fostering innovation</i>	Number of patents and licensing
	Number of innovations/patents co-developed with industry

KPIs are tools to measure the progress of a project. As such an aim for the KPIs need to be set at the beginning of every new reporting period. This will be the ambition to strive for by the end of the period. An example for an aim is 100 users served. This allows the evaluation of the progress in two ways: evaluating the aim on itself (Was the aim achieved? Was the aim not achieved and if so, how far off was the aim? Was the aim surpassed?), and comparing the aim with the achievement the year(s) before (Was the progress of the same magnitude? Was less or more achieved?). This allows evaluation of the progress isolated to the past reporting period and evaluation of the progress across the years. The latter will ensure that possible trends of progress stagnation can be recognised.

In 2026, expected values for KPIs for individual Nodes will be proposed based on planned capacities and in coordination with National Nodes coordinators. This will correspond to national specifics and namely the capacities available for EIRENE RI.

A reporting system will need to be set up that will enable efficient collecting and reporting of the data.

For now, biannual evaluation is proposed with an off-site evaluation (study of the KPIs and their background materials) and an on-site evaluation (on-site visit of selected EIRENE RI Nodes and/or Head Office and discussion with Node managers/directors and users).

14 Financial Plan

EIRENE's financial model covers the funding, costs, and financial sustainability throughout its lifecycle. This model is designed to support decision-making and ensure transparency, accountability, and long-term sustainability. As EIRENE aims to become an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium), its financial model will align with those of existing ERICs, particularly distributed research infrastructures like BBMRI, AnaEE, and ACTRIS. Distributed research infrastructures have a distinct structure compared to single-sited research infrastructures such as the European Spallation Source (ESS), resulting in different financial models. While both single-sited and distributed ERICs are established and governed under the ERIC Regulation, distributed research infrastructures (RIs) introduce additional financial complexities. These complexities arise from the fact that distributed RIs consist of multiple sites, often located in multiple countries, sometimes outside Europe. These circumstances lead to legal and financial challenges related to labor laws, multiple currencies, differing accounting and auditing rules, etc. Furthermore, some components (e.g., labs, services) may be included in the ERIC, while others are not, adding an additional layer of complexity.

Under the ERIC Regulation, the basic elements of the financial model must be included in the ERIC Statutes. Some ERICs, such as ACTRIS, include an annex to the statutes that details the contributions of members and observers to the operations. This annex outlines the principles of contributions and how they are calculated and provides an estimation of contributions for the first five years of operations.

This material serves as the starting point for the discussion about the extent of EIRENE-ERIC, the scale and scope of services and corresponding budgetary questions.

The Financial Model in the context of the final structure of EIRENE

The financial model is directly related to the governance structure of EIRENE-ERIC. As mentioned previously, the inherent structure of a distributed RI, such as EIRENE, introduces specific complexities with regard to the financial model because some components of the RI are part of the ERIC, while others are not. The final structure of EIRENE has not yet been determined, but it will substantially influence the final financial model. The diagram below illustrates the most probable option. A key component in the structure is the Central Coordination Units (CCUs). EIRENE-ERIC will deliver services across six key domains: Chemical Profiling, Toxicological Profiling, Biological Profiling, Environmental Samples & Data, Human Samples & Data, and Tools. Each service domain will potentially be managed at the EIRENE-ERIC level by a Central Coordination Unit hosted within the EIRENE-ERIC Head Office or by a Member/Observer. This domain-specific coordination is essential for ensuring operational efficiency and delivering high-quality services to users. Since individual institutions or laboratories may specialize in one or more domains, while others within the same country may focus on different or unrelated areas, coordination across domains, in addition to the National Nodes, is crucial for seamless operation. There are several options for hosting the CCUs, either within or outside the ERIC. While CCUs will legally be part of the ERIC, they can potentially be located in different research-performing organizations based on expertise. In that case, the CCUs will be dispersed across Europe. Inclusion in the ERIC ensures efficient coordination and utilization of the VAT and excise tax benefits given to ERICs. However, it might be complicated by the regulatory differences among the Member States (e.g., in labor laws). Furthermore, locating a CCU in a particular country means funding primarily from the hosting country. This means the host country will be required to pay an additional host (site) premium on top of the regular membership fee.

Other ERICs, such as ICOS and AnaEE, use a similar structure. ICOS, for example, has four Central Facilities (thematic centers), but unlike EIRENE, they are not part of the ERIC. AnaEE has three service centers within the ERIC and four national platforms outside the ERIC.

The Central Coordination Units will most likely be funded primarily through Host Contributions. The contributions will include cash and in-kind. In-kind contributions will be “paid” directly from the specific Host to the Central Coordination Unit located in their country, while the cash contributions will be paid to the EIRENE-ERIC and then redistributed to the Central Coordination Unit. Since the number and the organization of the CCUs has not been determined yet, the financial model cover primarily the head office. The existence and hosting costs of CCUs will be most probably held by hosting countries. The other possibility would be sharing the costs among all the ERIC members and redistributing to CCUs, but concerning current state of discussion, the first possibility is being more realistic.

Figure 4 Government structure of EIRENE-ERIC (plan)

Possible Financial Models

There are governance, management, operational, and financial consequences to including the Central Coordination Units within the ERIC. Since the decision regarding the final structure will be taken during the Implementation Phase, we have developed two potential financial models to account for these consequences.

1. Simple (compact) Structure Model

In the Simple Structure Model, EIRENE-ERIC will be streamlined, comprising solely of a Head Office. The Head Office will consist of the Director-General and support staff responsible for coordinating all EIRENE-ERIC activities. This model is cost-effective, with lower operational expenses compared to the Extended Structure Model. The costs (salaries, rents, operational costs, subcontracting) will be primarily covered by Member and Observer Contributions, eliminating the need for additional Host contributions. The simplicity of this model ensures easier management and coordination, with all activities centralized in one location.

2. Extended Structure Model

The Extended Structure Model is more expansive, including the Head Office and one or more Central Coordination Units. Similar to the Compact Structure Model, the Head Office will include the Director-General and support staff. The CC units will be established in various locations, enhancing the reach and capabilities of EIRENE-ERIC. The exact number and locations of these units will be determined during the Implementation Phase. While this model will significantly increase the total income and expenses of EIRENE-ERIC, it will have a relatively minor impact on Member and Observer Contributions as the additional costs associated with the Central Coordination Units

will be financed almost exclusively by Host Contributions. The table below summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of both models.

<i>Model</i>	<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Disadvantages</i>
<i>Compact Structure Model</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Easier management and coordination + Simplicity in structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potentially less influence and reach
<i>Extended Structure Model</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Enhanced influence and reach with multiple Central Coordination Units + VAT exemption on the purchase of equipment + Full access to finances of CCUs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased complexity in management and coordination - More complicated financial management and reporting due to differing accounting and auditing requirements among different countries.

Funding EIRENE

Funding for EIRENE will come from a variety of sources. It is important, however, to distinguish between the funding of EIRENE-ERIC and non-EIRENE-ERIC components. Non-EIRENE-ERIC components include any research facility, such as a lab that is part of EIRENE but not legally part of EIRENE-ERIC. These non-ERIC components will be connected to EIRENE-ERIC through service-level agreements (SLAs). This will apply to the majority of facilities.

Number of EIRENE-ERIC Members and Observers

The initial number of Members and Observers, i.e., Member States and Associated Countries that will establish the ERIC, will determine the funding capacity of EIRENE-ERIC. While EIRENE currently has 23 national nodes, it is unclear how many will eventually support the establishment of the ERIC and as such, how many will financially contribute to its operation. It is likely that initially, about half of the current member countries will become founding Members and Observers. This is a double-edged sword, as a smaller number of founding Members/Observers translates into higher Membership contributions per Member/Observer, which might deter potential Members/Observers from joining. The number of Members and Observers will directly impact the annual contributions since the operating costs of the EIRENE-ERIC Head Office are relatively fixed; a higher number of Members and Observers will translate into lower single annual contributions. It is expected that within several years, the number of members will increase, and thus, the financial burden of the founding members will decrease.

Current EIRENE members are listed below. Those we expect to participate and contribute to ERIC (based on current knowledge) are bold.

- | | |
|-------------------|------------------------|
| 1. Austria | 13. Netherlands |
| 2. Belgium | 14. Norway |
| 3. Cyprus | 15. Portugal |
| 4. Czechia | 16. Slovakia |
| 5. Denmark | 17. Slovenia |
| 6. Finland | 18. Spain |
| 7. France | 19. Sweden |
| 8. Germany | 20. United Kingdom |
| 9. Greece | 21. <u>USA</u> |
| 10. Iceland | 22. <u>Australia</u> |
| 11. Italy | 23. <u>Canada</u> |
| 12. Luxembourg | 24. <u>Japan</u> |

Types of Contributions

Similar to other distributed RIs, it is expected that the annual contributions will take two forms:

- **Member/Observer and**
- **Host/site contributions.**

Member and Observer contributions are the annual contributions for covering the operational costs of the EIRENE-ERIC Head Office, including personnel. These contributions also partially cover the cost associated with operating the Central Coordination Units. Member and Observer contributions can only be paid in cash. It is likely that the level of contributions of Members and Observers will be the same. This is exceptional as currently, the majority of RIs require lower contributions from Observers, e.g., around 30% of Member contributions.

The second type of contribution is **Host contribution** which is the portion of the contributions paid by a country (Member or Observer) hosting an EIRENE-ERIC Head office or Central Coordination Unit to its operations. Host contributions can be paid either cash or in-kind.

Methods of Contribution

Both cash and in-kind contributions will be utilized, depending on the situation. As mentioned above, Member and Observer contributions will only be allowed in cash, while Host contributions will be paid either in cash or in-kind. In-kind contributions lend themselves well to the academic and research fields, where resources such as equipment, facilities, and services can be provided directly. In-kind contributions are beneficial in various forms: providing access to specialized research equipment or laboratory space, offering technical support, data management, or administrative services, and assigning staff or researchers to work on specific projects or tasks within the RI. In-kind contributions can reduce the need for cash outlays by utilizing existing resources, thereby enhancing cost efficiency. They allow for the provision of highly specialized resources and expertise that might be difficult to procure with cash alone, offering specialized support. Additionally, in-kind contributions foster collaboration between institutions and integrate diverse resources into the RI's operations, promoting collaboration and integration.

Periodicity and Duration of Financial Commitment

The financial plan will be elaborated for five years. The five-year program will allow for ensuring the professional management and also planning of development of the whole research infrastructure. It will provide the essential stability of the EIRENE network and to the ERIC structure, which is essential for further development and fundraising. The program may be renegotiated if any of the countries would like to join the ERIC as the member of observer. The plans will be aligned to national programming to the best possible extent.

Sources of funding

EIRENE will be funded primarily through annual contributions from Members, Observers, and Hosts, European funding mechanisms, service provision, institutional contributions from participating organizations, and national funding of non-EIRENE ERIC facilities.

Member, Observer, and Host Contributions originate from EU Member States, Associated Countries, Third Countries, and Intergovernmental Organizations. As mentioned above, these will finance primarily the Head office, centrally provided services and possible CCUs.

European Funding Mechanisms include projects within the EU Framework Program (e.g., Horizon Europe) primarily. The development of EIRENE is funded through a dedicated INFRA-DEV Call, which funds the current EIRENE PPP project. An important source of funding for providing and developing services with other RIs is the INFRA-SERV Call. INFRA-SERVs constitute a significant source for allowing RIs to provide physical, remote, and virtual access to their services for free, based on competitive internal calls. Other research infrastructure dedicated calls, such as INFRA-EOSC, facilitate the integration of RIs with EOSC, INFRA-TECH, stimulating the cooperation and joint development of services with the industry will also be utilized. Furthermore, smaller funding for supporting the ERIC Forum, which consists of current and future ERICs and the various clusters such as ENVRI (environmental RIs cluster) and LS-RI (Life Science RIs cluster), is crucial for ensuring collaboration among existing RIs. It is important to keep in mind that there are many EU and nationally-funded projects that do not fund EIRENE activities directly, but rather provide funding for research projects in the exposome field, which contribute indirectly to EIRENE. This is the case of current second-pillar projects, which expect and support the participation of various research infrastructures and capacities. The development, position and allocation of the second pillar may become crucial for future development of not only EIRENE, the other RIs, but also the whole pan-European research environment.

User Service Fees constitute a minor source of funding due to the inherent not-for-profit nature of ERICs. The primary objective of ERICs, EIRENE included, is to provide services to the public research community on a nonprofit basis. Nonetheless, limited provision of service-for-fee is allowed under the ERIC Regulation.

Institutional contributions from participating organizations and national funding are the main sources for funding the non-EIRENE ERIC components (e.g., laboratories, research facilities, etc.). This includes both operational costs and capital investments.

The financial model and the ERIC regulation

The ERIC regulation impacts the financial model in several ways. Below there are key elements from the ERIC Regulation that must be considered in the financial model:

Budgetary Principles, Accounts, and Audit (Article 13)

To ensure comprehensive financial planning, all revenue and expenditure items must be included in the annual estimates. Maintaining a balanced budget is crucial, along with adhering to principles of sound financial management and transparency. Accounts must be prepared, filed, audited, and published as required by applicable law to uphold accountability and public trust.

Liability and Insurance (Article 14)

The financial liability of members for ERIC's debts must be clearly defined to ensure fairness and clarity. Additionally, provisions for insurance should be included to cover specific risks associated with the infrastructure, providing a safety net for unforeseen events.

Membership Contributions (Article 10(h))

Members are obligated to make contributions to maintain a balanced budget, ensuring the organization's financial stability.

Procurement Policy (Article 10(g)(vi))

The procurement policy must respect principles of transparency, non-discrimination, and competition. This ensures that procurement processes are fair, open, and competitive, fostering trust and efficiency in the use of resources.

Financial Reporting and Control (Article 17)

An annual activity report covering scientific, operational, and financial aspects must be produced. This report should be submitted to the Commission and relevant public authorities and made publicly available to ensure transparency and accountability in the organization's operations.

Winding-up and Insolvency (Article 16)

Procedures for winding up the ERIC and handling insolvency must be included to provide clear guidelines for these processes. The Commission must be notified, and an appropriate notice must be published in the Official Journal of the European Union to ensure compliance with legal requirements and public awareness.

Members and observers

Member A Member is typically a country or intergovernmental organization, that has formally joined the research infrastructure with full rights and responsibilities and are represented in the General Assembly. Members bear financial responsibility for the ERIC's operations through committed contributions according to the statutory funding model. Members hold voting rights in the ERIC's governing body (typically called the Assembly or General Assembly), with their voting weight agreed in the Statute. These voting rights allow Members to participate in strategic decision-making regarding the infrastructure's development, operations, and policies.

Members are entitled to full access to the research infrastructure's facilities, resources, services, and data according to the access policy established in the ERIC's governance documents.

Observer An Observer in an ERIC structure represents a transitional or partial participation state with limited rights and obligations compared to full Members. Observers are typically countries or intergovernmental organizations that have expressed formal interest in the ERIC but have not yet committed to full membership. This status may represent a stepping stone toward eventual membership or a long-term arrangement for entities with specific constraints. Observers generally make reduced financial contributions compared to full Members, often paying only a fraction of what would be required for full membership.

Observers typically hold limited or no voting rights in the ERIC's governance structure. They may attend Assembly meetings with speaking rights but cannot participate in formal decision-making processes unless specified otherwise in the ERIC's statutes. Observers receive restricted access to the research infrastructure's services, facilities, and resources as defined in the ERIC's access policy and observer agreements. Observer status often includes a defined timeframe after which the entity must either apply for full membership or withdraw from the ERIC structure, though extensions can be negotiated in some cases.

EIRENE-ERIC budget calculations

There are many ways how the budgets of ERICs are calculated. Usually, there are several components to take into account the size of the country, and size and level of the economy. Many ERICs use two basic components – fixed and variable. The fixed, targeting usually 40-60% of annual budget is usually represented by equal (or semi-equal) share of all the members. The variable one is usually derived from the size or the level of the economy (the higher the economy – GDP, or the higher the level of the economy – GDP pc, the higher the share on the variable budget). Alternatively, there may be the combination of GDP and GDP pc. In specific cases, the size of the country may be considered or there may be levels of GDP attributed to level of the contribution. These approaches are demonstrated below as an example how the EIRENE ERIC budget may be calculated.

5-year EIRENE RI Financial Plan

The 5-year EIRENE RI Financial Plan establishes the general framework for the proposed annual budget of the EIRENE ERIC and its central facilities (centrally provided services). This is based in current proposal, which is being discussed only internally. The 5-year financial plan sets the level of the Head Office Host premium contributions and Central Services Host contributions as well as the level of Membership contributions that the Members may pay. The initial 5-year Financial Plan for the EIRENE ERIC summarizes its expenditures and revenues for the considered years. Data and figures reported in the following tables are based on the calculations of the Coordinator and the level of services, which shall be provided in first five year. Importantly, these calculations will be further discussed with the partners (institutions) and the Board of Governmental Representatives once there is the agreement among the expected member states.

Table 6 EIRENE ERIC Cost structure

EIRENE-ERIC	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Personal costs					
Other costs					
TOTAL					
EIRENE-ERIC Head Office	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Personal costs					
Other costs					
TOTAL					
EIRENE-ERIC Reference laboratory (CZ)	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Personal costs					
Other costs					
TOTAL					
EIRENE-ERIC Data Center (CZ)	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Personal costs					
Other costs					
TOTAL					

The revenues of the EIRENE ERIC are composed by the Member states contributions, the host premiums to the Central Services, external projects (e.g. the HEU INFRA oriented and other research projects) and minor of the other resources. The distribution and foreseen values are presented in the table below.

Table 7 EIRENE-ERIC Revenues

EIRENE ERIC REVENUES	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Membership Contributions					
Host Contributions: Head Office					
Host Contributions: Central Coordination Units (CCU)					
External projects (HEU etc.)					
Other					
TOTAL					

Below provided table provides the detailed structure of the EIRENE Head office structure, which is based on expected scale and scope of the services provided centrally. We expect gradual increase of the staff efforts in first five years, which is evident from the budget proposal. The EIRENE Head Office will provide basic services, including the ELSI and QA/QC guidance, data policy framework, project services etc. The costs will also contain of the rent of premises and its usage, the travel costs to various meetings, organization of annual EIRENE meeting, communication etc.

Table 8 EIRENE Head office cost structure

ERIC HEAD OFFICE	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
PERSONAL COSTS					
Scientific director					
CEO					
Manager					
Open Access Manager					
Financial manager					
Project manager					
HR manager					
PR & communication					
ELSI specialist					
QA/QC / Accreditation expert					
Data specialist					
Rent, equipment maintenance					
Travel costs and meetings					
Office supplies & services (incl. IT)					
Communication and PR					
Consulting, subcontracts					
OA and Data services (ITC tools)					
ELSI Platform					
Annual conference costs					
TOTAL					

The EIRENE Reference laboratory plays a central role by providing specialized testing, validation, quality assurance, and expert guidance to other laboratories. Its main purpose is to ensure consistency, reliability, and high standards in laboratory results across a system, region, or network, which is absolutely key for the distributed research infrastructure developing new methodologies and implementing new services.

Table 9 EIRENE Reference lab budget structure

CCU Reference laboratory	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Staff costs					
senior scientific leader					
research specialist					
laboratory specialist					
QA/QC specialist					
Consumables					
Rent, equipment and maintenance costs					
TOTAL					

Data Centre is one of the core components of any distributed research infrastructure, the same will apply for the EIRENE RI. The ambition of the EIRENE Data Centre is to provide the services to all the National Nodes and the support to EIRENE RI users, incl. ensuring data integration and interoperability, Central Data Access Point, Data Governance and Compliance, IT safety and security, Data quality and standardisation etc. The costs are both staff costs and service costs.

Table 10 EIRENE Data Centre budget structure

CCU Data Center (CZ)	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5
Staff costs					
senior scientific leader					
senior programmer					
system architect					
programmer					
data analyst					
ICT administrator					
Services - data, cloud capacity, computational					
Rent, equipment and maintenance costs					
TOTAL					

National contribution is composed of the fixed budget contributions and variable budget contributions. The fixed contribution creates 40% and variable 60%, which is calculated according to the GDP. In the first version, we calculate the contribution paid by eleven member states and the second version the contribution is paid by fifteen member states – both filling the same amount of final budget.

Table 11 Member states contribution (11 countries)

	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5	share
Austria						
Belgium						
Czechia						
France						
Germany						
Greece						
Iceland						
Italy						
Netherlands						
Slovakia						
Slovenia						
TOTAL						

Table 12 Member states contribution (15 countries)

	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5	share
Austria						
Belgium						
Czechia						
Finland						
France						
Germany						
Greece						
Iceland						
Italy						
Netherlands						
Norway						
Slovakia						
Slovenia						
Spain						
UK						
TOTAL						

Several scenarios of EIRENE-ERIC budget calculations

There are many ways how the budgets of ERICs are calculated. Usually, there are several components to take into account the size of the country, and size and level of the economy. Many ERICS use two basic components – fixed and variable. The fixed, targeting usually 40-60% of annual budget is usually represented by equal (or semi-equal) share of all the members. The variable one is usually derived from the size or the level of the economy (the higher the economy – GDP, or the higher the level of the economy – GDP pc, the higher the share on the variable budget). Alternatively, there may be the combination of GDP and GDP pc. In specific cases, the size of the country may be considered or there may be levels of GDP attributed to level of the contribution.

EIRENE Cost Book

EIRENE Cost book is composed by the budgets of National Nodes, EIRENE-ERIC Head Office and EIRENE-ERIC Central Coordination Units (CCU) – namely the Data and Reference lab. The cost estimations are based on information received and provided by the EIRENE member countries, the coordinator and also based on the discussions with mature European Research infrastructures. The estimations are continuously updated to mirror the recent developments nationally.

To provide the full picture, overview of the whole EIRENE RI and also the background information, we provide following values:

- Investments already provided (National Nodes)
- Investments to be provided in next 5 years (National Nodes)
- Annual operation costs of the EIRENE-ERIC:
 - o Head Office
 - o CCU Data Services
 - o CCU Reference laboratory

Table 13 EIRENE Cost book (in EUR)

Country	Already Invested (until now, est.)	Expected investments (in the next 5 years)	Annual operating costs (est.)
Austria			
Belgium			
Cyprus			
Czech Republic			
France			
Germany			
Iceland			
Italy			
Netherlands			
Norway			
Portugal			
Slovakia			
Slovenia			
Spain			
Sweden			
UK			

The investments cover namely the costs of equipment and physical infrastructure realized in last five to twenty years. The following table and figure, on the other way, present the national investments, which should be realized in next 5 years, irrespectively on the sources available. Its scope depends both on the ambition and the current state of the National Nodes. One of the key types of information to plan the implementation and operation of the RI are the operational costs – and how they will be covered. Since this is not the financial plan, we provide only the cost side. The estimations may change and be adjusted accordingly once necessary. Below we also provide the comparison of expected costs within the whole EIRENE RI.

Figure 5 EIRENE Annual budget estimations (EUR, %)

15 Risk Management

The EIRENE management team maintains and continuously updates the registry of risks, which was developed at the beginning of the PPP project. The risks are divided into five categories - scientific, technological, political, financial, and organizational.

Below, we provide the overview of risks in defined categories: (Likelihood = L1-5, Impact = I1-5, Severity = S1-25, Mitigation strategy = M, Contingency action = C)

Scientific Risks (SR)

SR1: Lack of interest in MS, AC, and third countries (L2, I4, S8)

M: Partners engaged in designing EIRENE will actively communicate seeking national support.

C: Negotiation with the national coordinator and ESFRI delegates.

SR2: Disagreement over scientific orientation (L2, I3, S6)

M: Proper governing structure, partner involvement, and external advisory bodies.

C: National node representatives define a scientific strategy for approval.

SR3: Competing interests of institutions (L2, I5, S10)

M: Partner roles specified during the prep phase; synergized expertise.

C: Negotiation with nodes/RIs; ISAB consultation.

SR4: Low efficiency linking user needs and available technologies (L2, I5, S10)

M: Enhanced communication within/outside consortium; open technology access.

C: Strengthened national cooperation; increased regional/national promotion.

SR5: Lack of experienced personnel (L3, I5, S15)

M: Focus on skilled personnel recruitment and top technology.

C: Internal training; coordinated specialist hiring approach.

SR6: Delays in delivery of results (L3, I5, S15)

M: High-throughput technology, skilled personnel, good management.

C: Increased user communication to track outcomes.

Technological Risks (TR)

TR1: Technical problems causing user loss (L2, I3, S6)

M: Robust quality management process; immediate problem resolution.

C: Direct user communication; immediate issue resolution.

TR2: Unavailable technology demands (L2, I3, S6)

M: Alternative technologies proposed where possible.

C: User communication about technical feasibility and options.

TR3: Cross-border sample transfer issues (L3, I5, S15)

M: Establish procedures based on ethical guidelines and EU legislation.

C: Legal and specialist consultation.

TR4: Underutilized facilities (L2, I3, S6)

M: Enhanced communication efforts.

C: Selection process favoring appropriate sites; root cause analysis.

TR5: New infrastructure accommodation difficulties (L3, I5, S15)

M: Guidelines and training for new infrastructures; knowledge sharing.

C: Adoption of processes from experienced partners.

TR6: Data security and ethical risks (L3, I5, S15)

M: Comprehensive data management policy; ethical framework.

C: Immediate specialist consultation and resolution.

TR7: Market/capacity demand risks (L3, I3, S9)

M: Communicate capabilities to the scientific community; load distribution.

C: Strengthened user engagement; increased promotion.

TR8: Inefficient data workflow (L2, I5, S10)

M: Robust, regularly updated data management plan.

C: DMP refinement; EOSC specialist consultation.

Political Risks

PR1: Differing country resources/priorities (L4, I5, S20)

M: Leverage EU-level regulations; align with top EU priorities.

C: Engagement with national delegates and funding representatives.

P2: Conflicting policy agendas (L3, I5, S15)

M: Inform policymakers about EIRENE RI orientation and ongoing engagement.

C: National delegate and funding body communication.

P3: Legal/governance structure disagreements (L2, I4, S8)

M: Simple, flat, effective governance structure; experienced partners.

C: Governance discussions during PPP implementation.

Financial Risks

FR1: Failed socio-economic analysis (L2, I4, S8)

M: Analysis based on available data; detailed planning in the prep phase.

C: Root cause investigation (income vs. expenditure).

FR2: Insufficient national funding (L4, I5, S20)

M: Partner responsibility for operational resources; secured support letters.

C: Contact national/ESFRI representatives for alternative funding.

Organizational Risks

OR1: Consortium coordination issues (L2, I3, S6)

M: Experienced partners; professional management; proper systems.

C: Special resolution meetings as needed.

OR2: Head Office service quality issues (L2, I4, S8)

M: Staff training; service quality monitoring; capacity adjustment.

C: Performance management; work redistribution if needed.

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